

Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between perceived organizational support and organizational citizenship behaviour in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry. The five measures of organizational citizenship behaviour which we used as our criterion variable were altruism, conscientiousness, civic virtue, courtesy and sportsmanship. The study units comprised managers and workers and hence the corresponding level of analysis was the micro-level. The cross sectional survey was conducted with a sample size of 1450 workers drawn from a population of 3768 workers. The scales used were within the acceptable Cronbach Alpha values of 0.7, which was interpreted to be reliable. A total of 1,093 copies of completed and usable questionnaire was used for data analysis. Furthermore, descriptive statistics were computed at the primary level of analysis, while the Spearman Rank Order Coefficient was used at the secondary level of analysis. The result of the analysis showed that there is a positive and weak significant association between organizational support and altruism, civic virtue and sportsmanship, while a strong relationship was found between organizational support and conscientiousness and courtesy. The study finally recommends that management should develop support toward workers input that will promote personal well-being and enhance extra discretionary behaviour

Key words: *perceived organizational support, organizational citizenship behaviour, hospitality industry*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Organizations would not be in existence, if their members do not behave as good citizens by engaging in all sorts of positive organizational-relevant behaviour. As a consequence, the importance of good citizenship for organizations has been a high priority for organizational scholars and remains to be so (Bateman and Organ, 1983;

Organ, 1988). This growing concern has led scholars and practitioners to seek new concepts in organisational behaviour, one of which is organisational citizenship behaviour. It is noteworthy that not all behaviours at work can be captured by the formal job description of the organisation-man. Hence it is becoming obvious that organisation-members are gradually redefining work informally to include extra role, voluntary or spontaneous behaviours aimed at colleagues and the organisation at large (Organ *et al*, 2005).

From the later part of the last century, the place of discretionary extra role behaviour has gained increasing attention by researchers, managers, executives and employees as an essential ingredient to gain competitive advantage in the face of globalisation (Vigota-Gadot, 2007). Furthermore, Moideenkutty (2005) asserts that *OCB* has a particular impact on the overall effectiveness of organizations by adding to the social framework of

the work environment. Bukhari (2009) however attempts to make clearer the concept of *OCB* by drawing attention to the fluid nature of *OCB*. His description indicates that *OCB* can be construed as the social lubricant of the organizational machinery. As a result, Bolino *et al* (2004) argues that if it is an effective lubricant, then it can positively impact the organization and/or its members and consequently can be affected by instilling in employees a perception of expertise in their job tasks.

Having identified briefly the importance of *OCB*, it therefore becomes imperative to identify the factors that can influence *OCB* to enable organizations survive in an ever competitive environment. A growing need therefore has arisen to investigate factors that contribute to *OCB*. Consequently, in examining literature on *OCB*, we have been able to identify a dearth in factors that trigger off *OCB*. While research on the relationship between employee performance and *OCB* is abundant (Evans, 2011), there seems to be a dearth in the appropriate description of the relationship between POS and *OCB* in the Nigerian Workplace. Having identified this research gap, this study lays emphasis on Nigerian work organizations because at present, there is very little evidence that examines empirically, the relationship between POS and *OCB*, even though there is evidence of low level of workers' commitment in the country as pointed out

by Aluko, 2004. In this study therefore, we have examined the nature of perceived organizational support and its relationship with OCB in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry.

2.0 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT

It is generally acknowledged that employers of labour commonly hold to esteem employee dedication and loyalty, while on the other, employees are largely more concerned with the organization's commitment to them. For as argued by Eisenberger *et al* (2001), employees who are emotionally attached to the organization elicit increased performance, reduced absenteeism, and a decreased prospect of quitting their job. Kaufman *et al* (2001) argued that being valued by the organization can yield such benefits as approval and respect, pay and promotion, and access to information and other forms of aid needed to carry out one's job. Therefore, the norm of reciprocity allows employees and employers to reconcile these distinguishing orientations. Shore *et al* (2006) have further argued that exchange theorists have alluded to employment as the trade of effort and loyalty for tangible benefits and social rewards. The consequence of having such exchanges is that when one person treats another well because the reciprocity norm obliges the return of complimentary treatment. Hackett *et al* (2003) assert that to the extent that both the employee and the employer apply the reciprocity norm to their relationship, favourable treatment received by either party is reciprocated, leading to beneficial outcomes for both.

According to the perceived organizational support website, research on perceived organizational support began with the observation that if managers are concerned with their employees' commitment to the organization, employees are focused on the organization's commitment to them (<http://www.psychology.uh.edu/pos>).

Organizational support theory supposes that to determine the organization's eagerness to reward improved work effort and to meet socio-emotional needs, employees advance global beliefs concerning the extent to which the organization values their

contributions and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger *et al*, 1986 and Shore and Shore, 1995). They further argued that Perceived Organizational Support (*POS*) is also valued as assurance that aid will be available from the organization when it is needed to carry out one's job effectively and to deal with stressful situations. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) describe Perceived Organizational Support (*POS*) as the degree to which employees believe that their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. They assert further that *POS* is generally thought to be the organization's involvement to a positive reciprocity dynamic with employees, as employees tend to perform better to pay back *POS*. Coyle-Shapiro (2002) argue that for employees, the organization serves as an important source of socioemotional resources, such as respect and caring, and tangible benefits, such as wages and medical benefits. This is the reason behind the fact that being regarded highly by the organization helps to meet employees' needs for approval, esteem, and affiliation (Bell and Menguc, 2002).

2.2 ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

OCB is referred to as organizationally beneficial behaviours and gestures that can neither be enforced on the basis of formal employee's role obligations nor elicited by a contractual guarantee of recompense (Vigota-Gadot, 2007). Organizational Citizenship Behaviour as posited by Organ (1988) is conceptualised as individual behaviour that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization. Reiterating this view, Yen and Neihoff (2004) state that one of the challenging things about *OCB* is that there is no formal policy of reward in the organisation reward system. Three assumptions can be made from the original definition: (1) *OCB* is a discretionary behaviour; (2) it is not rewarded by any schedule or policy of remuneration; and (3) it promotes the effective functioning of the organisation.

By discretionary, Hui *et al* (2004) assert that the behaviour is not an enforceable requirement of the role or job description. This is likely to mean that it is not the clearly specifiable terms of the

person's employment contract with the organisation. Hence, the behaviour is rather a matter of personal choice, such that the omission is not generally understood as punishable (Ishak, 2005). On one hand, these spontaneous behaviours by individuals have played a key role in increasing the effectiveness, efficiency and positive climate in the workplace (LePine *et al*, 2002). On the other hand, managers and employees have been encouraged to increase their employees' voluntary activities in organizations

Coyle-Shapiro (2002) argue that for **OCB** to be an extra-role behaviour, it then must not formally be required by the organization, rather its practice depends solely on the consent of employee as a consequence of the organizational environment. This is based on the assumption that such behaviours create a healthier work environment, leads to improved work outcomes, and promotes the goals of the organization as a whole (Turnipseed and Rassuli, 2005). In as much as **OCB** is directed at co-workers within the workplace, it has positive effect on the organisation because in the long-term, it holds promise for the continual existence of the organisation (Kwantes, 2003).

The concept of **OCB** has been considered to have a plethora of measures (Organ, 1988). Smith *et al's* (1983) seminal conceptualization of **OCB** delineated a two-measure framework including altruism (behaviour targeted specifically at helping individuals) and generalized compliance (behaviour reflecting compliance with general rules, norms, and expectations). Since Smith *et al's* (1983) definition of organizational citizenship behaviour, there has been a lack of consensus regarding the measures of **OCB**. Despite all these, this study utilized the basic foundational measures of OCB as identified by Organ (1988). These five distinct measures of **OCB** comprise: altruism (helping behaviours directed at specific individuals), courtesy (informing others to prevent the occurrence of work-related problems), sportsmanship (tolerating the inevitable inconveniences of work without complaining), conscientiousness (going beyond minimally required levels of attendance), and civic virtue (participating in and being concerned about the life of the company).

2.3 PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND OCB

Perceived organisation support, which encompasses the belief that the organisation cares for and values its member's contribution to the success of the organisation (Kaufman *et al*, 2001), is important for the attainment of organisational goals. We argue here that as members experience an atmosphere of support, they tend to be more emotionally attached to the organisation and exhibit voluntary extra-discretionary behaviours. It therefore entails creating a supportive climate whereby workers experience a sense of duty at work and hence sees work as a central life interest rather than just a means to an end, which would elicit **OCB**. Furthermore, the perception that the organization values and cares about them may induce employees to incorporate organizational membership and role status into their self-identity (Eisenberger *et al*, 2002), and thus increase behaviours that are outside their job description which they carry out on behalf of the organization. Accordingly, Bell and Menguc (2002) assert that perceptions of organizational experience force the employee to evaluate their relations with the organizations.

In line with this, Jahangir *et al* (2004) empirically surmised that the employees who regard these exchanges fair tend to increase their dependence on organization and this increase encourages **OCB**. Similarly, Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) concluded that the relationship between **POS** and extra-role performance directed to the organization was higher than other categories of performance. It is assumed that employees balance their working efforts with the degree they perceive the organisation to respond with desirable returns (Cardona *et al*, 2004). We argue that a high climate of **POS** will therefore increase the organisation-man's sense of belongingness and hence would enable him exhibit extra-discretionary behaviours. We therefore hypothesize that:

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between organisational support and altruism in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry

H₀₂ There is no significant relationship between organisational support and

conscientiousness in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry

H₀₃ There is no significant relationship between organisational support and civic virtue in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry.

H₀₄ There is no significant relationship between organisational support and courtesy in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry

H₀₅ There is no significant relationship between organisational support and sportsmanship in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry

3.0 METHOD

The study units for data generation were individual organizational members and the micro-level of analysis was adopted. We adopted the concurrent methodological paradigm triangulation approach by combining both the Nomothetic and Ideographic methods of data collection and analysis. Hence, we administered both the questionnaire and conducted in-depth interviews in the data generation process. The study relied on extant literature for the survey instruments used to measure the study variables from where the instruments used were adapted 5 items out of the 36-items of Eisenberger et al (1986) for organizational support (earlier pretested by Rhoades and Eisenberger 2002) and five out of the 24 item OCB scale of Podsakoff et al (1980) to assess altruism, conscientiousness, civic virtue and courtesy and three were used for sportsmanship. We used a five-point Likert-type (modified Likert) scale for all the substantive variables in this study. Hence, undecided = 0; strongly disagree = 1; disagree = 2; agree = 3 and strongly agree = 4. The structured questionnaire that was used for this study were in two sections. Section One was structured to provide demographic information about the respondents, while section two elicited response on the study variables. The Cronbach's alpha

coefficients obtained for the test of reliability were above 0.7.

The population of this study was made up of hotels listed in the current updated directory of the State Ministry of Culture and Tourism in the six South-South Geo-political Zones made up of Bayelsa, Cross River, Akwa Ibom, Delta, Rivers and Edo States. We identified and utilised hotels in the State Capital with not less than 25 rooms, not less than 60 full time workers and with those having at least 7 out of the 10 facilities (Obiora, 2012). On the basis of this, stratified sampling was used to group each state into different strata where we had 8 hotels in Yenegoa, 10 hotels in Calabar, 6 hotels in Uyo, 5 hotels in Asaba, 12 hotels in Port Harcourt and 9 hotels in Benin City. We thus had a total of 50 hotels being utilised for our research. The 50 hotels had a total of 3768 workers, made up of Yenegoa, 600; Calabar 816; Uyo 517; Asaba 497; Port Harcourt 826 and Benin City 512. A sample size was drawn from the population of each state, using the Taro Yameni formula for sample size determination where we obtained a sample size of 240, for Yenegoa; Calabar 268; Uyo 226; Asaba 222; Port Harcourt 269 and Benin City 225. The total sample size obtained for all six states was 1450 (Table 1). The optimal allocation of the total sample size to each state was done using Proportionate Stratification Allocation Technique (*PSAT*).

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The primary and secondary levels of analysis were carried out. While frequencies and descriptives were used in our primary analysis, which focused on the study demographics, inferential statistics was applied at the secondary level of analysis. The response rate for field data collection is shown in table 1.

Table 1 reveals that 1093 copies of completed and usable questionnaire out of 1450 distributed were used for the analysis of the result. This represents a total response rate of 75.4%.

TABLE 1: RESPONSE RATE FOR FIELD DATA COLLECTION

S/No	State Capital	No. of Hotels	Population of Stratum	Sample Size of Stratum	Usable Sample Size	Subjects in each Hotel	Sampling Interval	copies Retrieved	Copies uncompleted	Copies completed but unusable	Copies completed and usable
1.	Yenegoa	8	600	240	231	28	3	226 (97.8%)	9 (3.9%)	36 (15.6%)	181 (78.4%)
2.	Calabar	10	816	268	314	31	3	246 (78.3%)	12 (3.8%)	28 (8.9%)	206 (65.6%)
3.	Uyo	6	517	226	199	33	3	190 (95.5%)	9 (4.5%)	5 (2.5%)	176 (88.4%)
4.	Asaba	5	497	222	191	38	3	182 (95.3%)	6 (3.1%)	23 (12.0%)	153 (80.1%)
5.	Port Harcourt	12	826	269	318	27	3	238 (74.8%)	19 (6.0%)	9 (2.8%)	210 (66.0%)
6.	Benin City	9	512	225	197	22	3	188 (95.4%)	14 (7.1%)	7 (3.6%)	167 (84.8%)
TOTAL		50	3768	1450	1450						TOTAL : 1093 (75.4%)

SOURCE: Research Survey, 2011

Demographic characteristics: JOB STATUS: out of a total of 1093 respondents, 23 (10.7%) in Yenegoa, 56 (26.2%) in Calabar, 22 (10.3%) in Uyo, 28 (13.1%) in Asaba, 57 (26.6%) in Port Harcourt and 28 (13.1%) in Benin were managers. This gave a total of 214 managers in the six states. . Also, 158 (18.0%) in Yenegoa, 206 (18.8%) in Calabar, 176 (16.1%) in Uyo, 153 (14.0%) in Asaba, 210 (19.2%) in Port Harcourt and 167 (15.3%) in Benin represents junior staff.

Job Experience: Respondents were asked to state their years of experience in the hotel industry. This is a very vital information in this study because citizenship behaviour at the workplace requires time to manifest. 32 respondents representing 12.5%, 76 or 14.4%, 70 (24.7%), 3 (11.1%) of 181 respondents in Yenegoa have spent less than five years, five to ten years, eleven to fifteen years and 16 years and above respectively in the industry. Also, 33 (12.9%), 122 (23.1%), 49 (17.3%), 2 (7.4%) of 206 respondents in Calabar have spent

less than five years, five to ten years, eleven to fifteen years and sixteen years and above in the industry. In Uyo, 29 (11.4%) have spent less than five years, 119 (22.5%) have spent five to ten years, 26 (9.2%) have spent eleven to fifteen, 2 (7.4%) have spent 16 years and above in the industry.

Out of the 153 respondents in Asaba, 21 (8.2%) have spent less than five years, 113 (21.4%) have spent 5 to 10 years, 17 (6.0%) have spent 11 to 15 years and 2 (7.4%) have spent 16 years and above in the industry. In Port Harcourt, 98 or 34.6% respondents, which represents a majority of the respondents have spent between eleven to fifteen years in the industry, while in Benin, a majority of respondents, that is 105 (41.2%) have spent less than five years in the industry.

4.1 Bivariate analysis

The result of the Spearman rank Correlation Coefficient for the relationship between organizational support and organizational citizenship is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for Organizational Support and Measures of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

			POS	ALT	CSC	CIV	CSY	SPT
Spearman's rho	POS	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.292(**)	.302(**)	.284(**)	.322(**)	.285(**)
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093
	ALT	Correlation Coefficient	.292(**)	1.000	.986(**)	.993(**)	.991(**)	.992(**)
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093
	CSC	Correlation Coefficient	.302(**)	.986(**)	1.000	.951(**)	.929(**)	.931(**)
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093
	CIV	Correlation Coefficient	.284(**)	.993(**)	.951(**)	1.000	.987(**)	.987(**)
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093
	CSY	Correlation Coefficient	.322(**)	.991(**)	.929(**)	.987(**)	1.000	.985(**)
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093
	SPT	Correlation Coefficient	.285(**)	.992(**)	.931(**)	.987(**)	.985(**)	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
		N	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093	1093

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

SOURCE: research data, 2011

Although weak, Organizational Support positively correlated to altruism ($r = 0.292, p 0.000 < 0.01$). Also, Organizational Support (*POS*) is significantly and positively correlated to conscientiousness (*CSC*) ($r = 0.302, p 0.000 < 0.01$). Though weak, Organizational support is significantly and positively correlated to civic virtue (*CIV*) ($r = 0.284, p 0.000 < 0.01$). Organizational Support is also significantly and positively correlated to courtesy (*CSY*). Finally, organizational support is weakly significant and positively related to sportsmanship (*SPT*) $r = .285, p 0.000 < 0.01$. Consequently, the relationship between organizational support and measures of organizational citizenship behaviour is thus significant at the 0.01 level of significance.

5.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

We have found in this study that the Nigerian Hospitality Industry is characterised by workers who believe that their organizations value their contributions and cares about their well-being. In other words, these organizations take into account their workers input and personal well-being. This is corroborated by Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) when they argue that in supportive organisations, ‘employees evidently believe that the organization has a general positive or negative orientation toward them that encompasses both their contributions and their welfare. For workers, they assert further that the organization serves as an important source of socio-emotional resources, such as respect and caring, and tangible benefits, such as wages and medical benefits. These results corroborates those of our oral interview with organization members.

Drawing from this view, our findings suggest that within the Nigerian Hospitality Industry, when workers perceive their organization

as being willing to assist them when they need a special favour and the organization is also willing to extend itself in order to help them perform their job to the best of the worker's ability, it creates an atmosphere which drives members to harmoniously work towards the achievement of set goals. We emphasise here that a primary rationale for the organizational support practice is to generate a profitable assessment of the organization by the employees, which would increase employees' felt obligation to help the organization reach its objectives, outside the norm of prescribed work functions. Furthermore, within the industry, organizational support seems to create a sense of obligation toward the organization that trigger off positive social interactions, such that behavioural outcomes of perceived organisational support would include increases in extra-role performance.

As the support given by the organization becomes clearer and more manifest, the workers tend to pursue actions favourable to the organization that go beyond assigned responsibilities. According to George and Brief (1992), such voluntary extra role activities include aiding fellow employees, taking actions that protect the organization from risk, offering constructive suggestions, and gaining knowledge and skills that are beneficial to the organization. As suggested by Coyle-Shapiro (2002), a worker with high perception of organizational support who tend to believe that the organization has his or her best interest at heart, would be inclined to reciprocate by venturing into extra discretionary behaviours. This is important for the Hospitality Industry because as Asgari *et al* (2008) empirically reports that 'the higher the level of perceived organizational support, the more likely is the individual to perform discretionary extra role behaviours'. Based on the norm of reciprocity, perceived organisational support suggests that the reason that workers who believe that they receive a higher level of support from the organisation perform better in discretionary work behaviours, is that they feel obligated to care about the organization and help meet its objectives through positive attitude and behaviours towards the organisation. It is therefore imperative for any organization that desires competitive advantage in the ever increasing globalised competitive market to row on the oars of

workers tendency to assign the organization humanlike characteristics.

We have shown that a supportive work environment is weakly associated with co-worker helpfulness. Our results do not corroborate with those of who Eisenberger *et al* (2001) and Kraimer and Wayne, (2004), who have shown with empirical evidence that gives us an indication that a supportive organization is associated with increased discretionary helpfulness. It is in this regard that Bachrach (2006) affirm that organizational support is a potentially influential tool for generating high levels of eliciting discretionary co-worker helpfulness or altruism, outside the nominal job requirements. In line with this, Loi *et al* (2006) therefore explain that a positive perception of organizational support has a direct effect on the level of worker helpfulness. We find on the contrary that as the organisation meets the work and personal wellbeing of its workforce, it does not strongly propel the worker to voluntarily lend a helping hand to colleagues. In our interview, some respondents opined that their work load is usually so heavy that despite the support given to them by their organization, there is little or no time to assist others. Others said that any leisure time they had enabled them have their rest and they do not really look forward to assisting others.

Consequently, we have found that as workers of the Nigerian Hospitality industry perceive their organization as supportive, they substantially develop a sense of conscientiousness toward the organization. This reciprocity implies that as the organisation meets the work and personal need for the personal development of the worker, it tends to increasingly create a sense of belonging to the organization, and make them feel that they ought to voluntarily go the extra mile outside the nominal job requirement. Our finding here is in line with Loi *et al's* (2006) empirical validation that asserts that individuals exhibiting high conscientiousness are known to be punctual. We find in this study that worker conscientiousness develops when the organization has been seen to be supportive.

As we find in the case of the hospitality industry, when the worker's interest is taken into consideration, it enhances their punctuality and they go further to obey company rules and regulations

even when no one is watching. Accordingly, in line with our findings Asgari *et al* (2008) points out that according to organizational support theory, if employees perceive more support from the organization, they are likely to show greater attendance and efforts, which in turn, lead to better performance.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

From the foregoing analysis, the findings that emerged here are (1) As organizations in the Nigerian Hospitality industry take into account the worker input and personal well-being, the worker weakly exhibits extra role helping behaviours outside their job descriptions; (2) In the Nigerian Hospitality Industry, organizational members' voluntary behaviours that go beyond the minimum role requirement is influenced by the understanding of the organization toward the worker's input and personal well-being; (3) As organisations in the Nigerian Hospitality Industry give support to their workers, the worker weakly goes beyond his job description to protect the image of this organization; (4) In the Nigerian Hospitality Industry workers display extra role discretionary polite gestures to prevent work related problems when the organization is seen to provide support to them towards their work input and personal wellbeing and (5) The willingness of workers to discretionarily tolerate annoyances at work without complaining, is weakly demonstrated when the organization provides support to their workers toward their personal well-being and work input.

It therefore behoves that the organization takes into account their workers input and personal well-being. Furthermore, it was established that this being present, it propels the workers to harmoniously work toward the actualisation of organisational goal, outside the norm of prescribed job description. Such behavioural outcomes we have earlier noted weakly triggers off co-worker helpfulness, propels a strong sense of conscientiousness, a weak demonstration of civic virtue, a strong display of courtesy and a weak exhibition of sportsmanship.

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